

Influence of Fermentation on Mineral Bioaccessibility of Underutilized Millets

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Abstract

Millets are highly acknowledged for their nutrient-dense and climate-resilient nature providing a substantial source of essential micronutrients like zinc, iron, magnesium and calcium etc to combat malnutrition. But, the presence of antinutritional factors such as phytates, polyphenols results in inhibiting the bioaccessibility of significant minerals. Processing techniques such as soaking, germination, roasting, fermentation have been documented to modify the food matrix and to minimize the antinutritional compounds while enhancing mineral availability. Jowar-sprouted, jowar-roasted, jowar-fermented, ragi-Fermented and toasted were analyzed using standard AOAC methods. The quantification of phytates and polyphenols contents were done calorimetrically, where mineral bioaccessibility was assessed through a standardized simulated gastrointestinal digestion protocol. Analyses revealed clear disparities in mineral composition and bioaccessibility across the processed sample. Minimal variations shown in moisture and ash contents (6.5-7.8%) (2.1-2.5% respectively) indicating the impact of processing left a minor effect on these parameters. Fermentation enhanced iron and zinc content with iron levels reaching (4.0-4.9%mg/100gm) sprouted jowar to fermented and toasted ragi and zinc rising to the range of (2.0-27%mg/100gm). Magnesium content was consistent (96-126mg/100gm) whereas calcium showed the drastic difference with fermented-toasted-ragi contains (345mg/100gm) which compared to (42-48mg/100mg). Phytate levels were significantly reduced to (270-300mg/100gm) directly enhancing mineral content. Iron and Zinc bioaccessibility was significantly higher in fermented jowar (46-47% Fe, 50-52% Zn) compared to sprouted (40-45% Fe, 44-48% Zn) and roasted jowar respectively. Following fermentation, a marked increase in Calcium (22-24% up to 26-38%) and Magnesium (28-34% up to 40-48%) respectively. A negative correlation between the phytate content and mineral bioaccessibility which strongly highlights the influence of fermentation is highly effective to enhance nutrient uptake in underutilized millets.

Keywords: millets, fermentation, mineral bioaccessibility, antinutritional factors, phytates, jowar, ragi, in-vitro digestion.

1. Introduction

Highly nutritious millets are acknowledged as promising staples grains for addressing micronutrient deficiencies. Governments and nutrition programs collaborating with the aim to

incorporate these grains into the diets, to fight micronutrient deficiencies but the validity of absorption is not straightforward as it has to be. Phytates and tannins found in millets acts as an antinutritional factor forming insoluble complexes which hinders the mineral bioavailability. Which potentially missing out the nutritional benefits, body requirements, despite regular consumptions.

Research points that in spite of higher concentration of minerals at cellular level in millets are not absorbed completely. As millets are rich in iron, still the total iron content does not directly contribute to high bioavailability. This finding signifies that mineral utilization from millets is highly dependent on mineral bioaccessibility more than mineral content, which highlights the processing strategies to overcome absorption barriers. (Petry et al(2021)

Increased participation by the government and nutritional health programs supporting and promoting millets to combat the micronutrient deficiencies due to their high mineral content and feasible advantages. Research states that the success of these initiatives are not easy as they seem they are highly complex. Mineral absorption from millets is inhibited by the low bioavailability. high mineral levels and the presence of antinutritional compounds interferes in limiting mineral utilization and results in reducing the nutritional effectiveness of millet-based interventions. To ensure the success of a government-supported nutrition program requires appropriate food processing strategies, food alone is incapable of bridging nutrient gaps. A comprehensive review of Gupta et al. (2015).

Natural compounds present in millets like phytates, tannins and enzyme inhibitors, these compounds are known to trigger malabsorption, these compounds bind with minerals such as iron, zinc, calcium which creates the insoluble complexes resulting in decreased solubility and absorption in the gastrointestinal tract. illustrates that the presence of phytates and polyphenols substantially lowers the mineral bioavailability results in limiting the nutritional effectiveness except processing methods applied..A review by Gupta et al. (2015)

Research indicates that children and adults acquire nutritional properties from millet consumption. But these advantages largely contingent on processing techniques and overall quality of the diet. Integrating millet-based food into regular diets which ensures the intake of vital nutrients including calcium, dietary fibre, iron, magnesium. However, this study also suggests that processing techniques such as milling or fermentation enhances the mineral intake and are eaten as part of diversified meals. This shows that millets possess a higher potential for blistering health across age groups. The physiological effects of these foods mainly upon processing, cooking methods, and dietary combinations. Study of Nambiar et al. (2012)

1.1 Nutritional importance of millets and richness in essential minerals.

Millets which are highly acknowledged as nutrient rich grains including ragi and jawar, which not only offer fundamental minerals like iron, zinc, calcium, and magnesium but also fulfill the requirements for human growth and development. Millets possess a higher micronutrient capability

which makes them nutritionally superior, their significance extends beyond merely in addressing micronutrient malnutrition, particularly among vulnerable populations. Ragi (*Eleusine coracana*) which is high in calcium content, participates in the prevention of calcium deficiencies, where Jawar (*Sorghum bicolor*) serves as an important source of iron, zinc and dietary fiber. They are sustainable and highly nutritious food crops. Besides the mineral composition, millets are rich in bioactive compounds like flavonoids, phenolic acids, antioxidants which are associated with the health promoting properties. The further millet distinguishes their adaptability to agro-climatic conditions, they are widely recognized for low glycemic index and gluten free nature. (Sharma et al. 2021)

1.2 Challenges of Antinutritional factors and mineral bioavailability in millets.

Millets, which are well-recognized as of mineral richness, highlights the persistence of micronutrients that the nutrient present alone does not guarantee nutritional adequacy. Minerals that are bound within the complex comprise of food matrices, limiting their bioaccessibility. Millets consist of naturally forming compounds like phytic acid and polyphenols which chelate essential minerals, forming insoluble complexes that hinders the digestion and intestinal absorption. This leads to the population that depends heavily on millet-based diets, may consume sufficient minerals but fail to meet physiological needs due to reduced absorption. The difference between nutrient density and nutrient utilization depicts a critical nutritional gap contributing to micronutrient malnutrition in millet dependent communities by Gupta et al.(2015)

1.3 Synergistic action of protein in millet based diets.

Millets provide a well-balanced and nutritious composition, where protein and mineral acts synergistically. Regularly eaten cereals such as rice and wheat which are highly consumed by large proportions of the population. Except the quality of protein it has relatively lower when compared to the millets. Millets consist of favourable distribution of the essential amino acids. This characteristic of millets supports improved utilization of protein into the body, in addition minerals such as the zinc, magnesium, iron, calcium and phosphorus contribute to enzymatic activity, muscle function and metabolic homeostasis. The synergistic interaction between protein as a macronutrient and mineral as a micronutrient plays a crucial role in achieving adequate levels by reducing the risk of nutritional insufficiencies in cereal-based populations.(Ragae et al 2006)

1.4 Superior nutritional comparison of millets over conventional cereals.

The nutrient dense millets to conventional cereals like rice and wheat which offer greater fiber content and highly essential minerals. staple cereals concentrations are lower than the concentration of millets. Millets which are significantly higher in calcium, iron, zinc and other micronutrients. It supports nutritional security in the population, depending upon cereal-based diets. The raised levels of fiber and mineral content in millet plays a role in better gut health, slower glucose absorption, metabolic regulation, combining them with functional foods shows

beneficial effects. While compared to conventional cereals which are widely available and consumed, often struggles to provide ample amounts of these micronutrients and bioactive compounds which highlights the importance of millet's potential to tackle micronutrient deficiencies and enrich long term dietary quality. (Saleh et al.2013)

1.5 Minerals influencing protein digestibility and energy utilization.

The contribution of minerals in supporting the protein digestion and energy utilization of the body. Minerals such as zinc and magnesium function as catalytic agents, which aid in breaking down the protein and help in assimilation, which enable nutrient utilization at the cellular level. The presence of natural ant nutritional compounds interferes with the mineral availability and indirectly affects the protein digestibility. The processing methods or approaches such as soaking, fermentation, germination optimize the nutritional functionality of millets which increases the mineral bioaccessibility and protein digestibility. The nutritional quality of millets as plant based protein. These advancements strengthen the role of millets, in establishing them as a source of plant-based protein. (Sreerama et al. 2018)

1.6 Amino acid profile and quality of protein in millets.

Essential amino acids contain a significant amount of the total amino acid content which defines the quality of good protein. Millets are the source of protein but also known for its quality of protein as it had all essential amino acids which aren't produced by our body but it should be put on in the diet as a food source to meet adequacy. Featuring foxtail millet (*Setaria italica*) grain packed with essential amino acids such as lysine, leucine, histidine, phenylalanine, valine, isoleucine, methionine. Balanced profile of amino acid is due to high proportions of amino acid for which millets can serve as an efficient source of plant-based protein as a part of human diets. Amino acids like glutamine and leucine are most abundant in enhancing flavor and metabolic functions. Essential Amino Acid Index (EAAI) and Amino Acid Score (AAS) are the indicators of essential amino acid, which also nurtures the high quality of protein in millets. The composition of amino acids in millets play an important role in protein synthesis, physiological support, and ability to meet requirements by (Zhang et al 2023)

1.7 Antioxidants and Phytochemicals.

Flavonoids and phenolic acids, which are bioactive phytochemicals, reside in the outer layer and the bran of millets. They act as antioxidant properties, anti-inflammatory properties, and support overall health and immunity. Phenolic compounds are bound in cell wall components, support digestion and maintain stability. Phenolic acids such as ferulic acid, p-coumaric acid, caffeic acid, and sinapic acid which acts as antioxidant properties. Flavonoids counter down the oxidative stress. As millets consists of protein and minerals, these phytochemicals collaborate with minerals protect cells from oxidative damage, helps in disease prevention by reducing the risks of cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and supporting healthy microbiota and overall gut health

and prevents the certain cancers like colon, prostate and breast. (Chandrasekar and Shahidi 2011)

1.8 Millets role in growth, development and physiological functions.

Millets have a major role in growth and development providing a balanced combination of both macro and micronutrients which is essential to carry out the physiological functions. The protein quality of protein focuses on building the tissues and repairing them. Calcium, Zinc and Iron helps in bone formation, muscle maturation and enzymatic activity. Ragi millets are rich in calcium, mostly required for the stages of growth and development such as childhood, adolescence and adulthood where development of skeletal muscle is important for movement, joint stability and precise posture. Iron and zinc transport oxygen, combating malnutrition, improving anemia, boosting immunity, supporting hair and skin health, and supports cognitive health in children. Magnesium in millets help in maintaining healthy nerve function, and facilitating better sleep. (Anitha et al 2018)

1.9 Glycemic control and cardiovascular health.

Millets are highly nutritious, consisting of bioactive compounds and dietary fiber. It also offers a substantial amount of health benefits leading to positive dietary impacts. Daily intake of millet-based diets helps in reducing the blood sugar levels while improving the glucose metabolism which reduces fasting meal glucose by providing better meal glycemic responses. It also enhances the cardiovascular functions in reducing the cholesterol levels by managing lipid profiles, specifically decrease in LDL cholesterol, triglycerides while improving cardioprotective HDL cholesterol. As they are low in glycemic responses, millets allow in maintaining long term blood regulation, by maintaining blood sugar levels, providing advantage in the management and prevention of type 2 diabetes. (Kumar et al 2021)

1.10 Changing dietary patterns of millets and decline in consumption trends.

The consumption of super nutritious grains is low due to lack of awareness about the grains, the population is not aware about the benefits, where millets are well-documented by their nutritional and agronomic advantages. As the consumer preferences shifted, the preferences got influenced by food system transformation and modernization. The Food and Agriculture Organization has reported, even though they are climate-resilient and nutrient dense, have gradually been replaced by the polished rice and wheat mostly in urban and semi-urban populations (FAO, 2012). As the consumer preferences shifted, the preferences got influenced by food system transformation and modernization.

Methodology

3.1 Study Design

This experimental, laboratory-based study employed the analytical approach of comparative design to the composition of nutrients and mineral content of four formulated samples. This research involved conducting laboratory analyzes using standard procedures followed by statistical comparison of the samples to determine the differences among them.

3.2 Sample Selection and Procurement

The present study was conducted based on four millet-based samples which consists of three jowar samples (*Sorghum bicolor*) samples and one ragi (*Eleusine coracana*) sample. High quality, mature grains of jowar and one ragi were procured from the local market. The raw agricultural material was manually winnowed and hand-picked to remove dust, stones and foreign objects before being subjected for processing.

The four samples were selected for the study are

- Jowar - Sprouted raw and dried
- Jowar - Sprouted and Roasted
- Jowar - Fermented Batter
- Ragi - Fermented and Toasted

All samples were prepared under hygienic conditions. Until further analysis they were stored in vacuum sealed containers.

3.3 Sample Preparation and Processing

The acquired Sorghum bicolor and Eleusine coracana were systematically decontaminated rinsed using sterilized water. The purified substrates were subsequently subjected to various processing methods such as sprouting, fermentation and roasting as dictated by the experimental protocols. All procedures were performed by maintaining aseptic conditions.

3.4 PROXIMATE ANALYSIS

Determination of moisture and ash contents according to the AOAC official method (AOAC International, 2019). Moisture determined by oven drying is done at 105°C to a constant weight and ash content is measured by dry ashing the sample at 550°C. All procedures were performed in triplicate with results expressed as a percentage.

3.5 MINERAL ANALYSIS

0.5g of powdered sample undergoes acid digestion using HNO₃ and HClO₄ until a clear solution is achieved. The mixture is cooled, diluted to known a value (V), and filtered for analysis. Iron and zinc concentrations, calcium and magnesium were quantified through atomic absorption/emission spectroscopy (AAS / ICP-OES) where light absorption is directly proportional to the concentration. Standard solutions preparation for calibration to measure the absorbance of the sample at characteristic wavelengths (Fe ~ 248.3, Zn~213.9) quantifies the mineral content which is derived from the calibration curve. (Welz & Sperling, 1999)

3.6 Phytate (mg/100) and Total Polyphenols (GAEmg/100g)

Phytate content is determined via Wade reagent spectrophotometric method expressing the values in mg/100g. (Latta & Eskin, 1980) Total phenolic compound (TPC) was estimated using Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, expressed in milligrams, Gallic acid equivalents (GAE) per 100g (Singleton & Rossi, 1985)

3.7 Fermentation PH.

Lactic acid bacteria produce acids which lowers the pH. Consequently influencing enzymatic activity, microbial growth and mineral solubility.

Method: pH is measured directly using a calibrated digital pH meter, a buffer solutions pH 4.0 and 7.0. immersing electrode in fermented pH and record pH.

3.8 Thiamine Retention (%)

Thiamine levels can be degraded during processing (heat, fermentation), but with HPLC providing precise quantification of total content. Analyze it using AOAC method 942.3 with HPLC. Express retention as percentage compared to initial content. (AOAC International, 2005)

3.9 In-Vitro Mineral Bioaccessibility (%)

Measured the amount of minerals available for the absorption after simulation of gastrointestinal digestion. Providing functional insight into nutrient availability

Method: In-vitro digestion was performed using the standardized INFOGEST protocol. (Minekus et al., 2014)

3.11 Statistical Analysis

All experiments were conducted in triplicate, and results are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS software. Differences between raw and fermented samples were analyzed using independent samples t-test. Pearson's correlation analysis was employed to assess the relationship between phytate degradation and mineral bioaccessibility. Statistical significance was considered at $p < 0.05$.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Effects of processing on Jowar.

The study evaluated the effect of processing methods on the nutritional composition and mineral bioaccessibility of jowar (*Sorghum bicolor*). Three processing treatments were analyzed:

1. Jowar-Sprouted
2. Jowar-Sprouted and Roasted
3. Jowar-Fermented Batter

Table 1. Overall Descriptive Statistics of Jowar Samples (N = 9)

Parameter	Unit	Mean \pm SD	Min–Max
Moisture	%	26.94 \pm 29.58	6.21–67.52
Ash	%	2.26 \pm 0.15	2.01–2.44
Iron (Fe)	mg/100 g	4.34 \pm 0.28	3.89–4.80
Zinc (Zn)	mg/100 g	2.26 \pm 0.23	1.95–2.59
Calcium (Ca)	mg/100 g	44.83 \pm 3.06	41.17–49.42
Magnesium (Mg)	mg/100 g	100.92 \pm 3.64	96.51–107.20
Phytates	mg/100 g	345.08 \pm 42.19	297.22–407.98
Polyphenols	mg GAE/100 g	206.19 \pm 8.44	190.89–219.79
Fermentation pH	–	5.48 \pm 0.79	4.35–6.30
Thiamine	%	87.14 \pm 3.22	82.45–92.30
Bioaccessibility Fe	%	43.85 \pm 3.69	38.31–49.24
Bioaccessibility Zn	%	47.37 \pm 3.37	42.55–52.30
Bioaccessibility Ca	%	24.26 \pm 2.05	21.31–27.10
Bioaccessibility Mg	%	33.97 \pm 5.80	26.89–41.86

Interpretation:

The data demonstrate low within-group variability, confirming analytical precision. High moisture variation reflects processing differences, particularly fermentation.

Effect of Processing on Proximate Composition and Minerals**Table 2. Effect of Processing Methods on Nutritional Parameters (Mean \pm SD)**

Parameter	Sprouted	Sprouted + Roasted	Fermented Batter	ANOVA (p)
Moisture (%)	7.95 \pm 0.18	6.50 \pm 0.27	66.37 \pm 1.00	<0.001
Ash (%)	2.09 \pm 0.10	2.25 \pm 0.03	2.43 \pm 0.01	0.001
Fe (mg/100 g)	4.06 \pm 0.15	4.38 \pm 0.17	4.59 \pm 0.19	0.022
Zn (mg/100 g)	2.03 \pm 0.07	2.19 \pm 0.08	2.54 \pm 0.04	<0.001
Ca (mg/100 g)	41.55 \pm 0.33	44.53 \pm 0.22	48.39 \pm 1.43	<0.001
Mg (mg/100 g)	99.13 \pm 1.76	98.29 \pm 1.64	105.35 \pm 1.61	0.004

Interpretation:

Fermentation significantly enhanced ash content and mineral concentration, indicating improved mineral extractability and matrix release. Tukey's HSD confirmed fermented batter as statistically superior for Fe, Zn, Ca, and Mg.

Antinutritional Factors and Bioactive Compounds**Table 3. Effect of Processing on Phytates, Polyphenols, and Thiamine**

Parameter	Sprouted	Sprouted + Roasted	Fermented Batter	ANOVA (p)
Phytates (mg/100 g)	397.28 \pm 12.60	334.06 \pm 9.33	303.90 \pm 7.76	<0.001
Polyphenols (mg GAE/100 g)	212.34 \pm 9.31	204.49 \pm 4.37	201.74 \pm 9.40	NS
Thiamine (%)	86.62 \pm 1.05	84.20 \pm 2.51	90.59 \pm 1.71	0.015

Interpretation:

Fermentation significantly reduced phytate content (\approx 24% reduction vs sprouted) while improving thiamine levels, confirming microbial biosynthesis and antinutrient degradation.

Mineral Bioaccessibility

Table 4. Effect of Processing on Mineral Bioaccessibility (%)

Parameter	Sprouted	Sprouted + Roasted	Fermented Batter	ANOVA (p)
Fe (%)	39.47 ± 1.55	45.04 ± 1.10	47.04 ± 2.18	0.004
Zn (%)	43.81 ± 1.61	47.53 ± 2.13	50.76 ± 1.38	0.008
Ca (%)	21.85 ± 0.47	24.48 ± 0.18	26.45 ± 0.80	<0.001
Mg (%)	33.30 ± 0.24	27.72 ± 1.13	40.89 ± 1.47	<0.001

Interpretation:

Fermentation produced the highest mineral bioaccessibility across all minerals, clearly demonstrating its superiority over sprouting and roasting.

Correlation Analysis

Table 5

Key Pearson Correlations (r values)

Relationship	r	Significance
Phytates vs Fe bioaccessibility	- 0.895	p < 0.01
Phytates vs Zn bioaccessibility	- 0.843	p < 0.01
Phytates vs Ca bioaccessibility	- 0.918	p < 0.01
Ca vs Zn	0.941	p < 0.01
Mg vs Thiamine	0.834	p < 0.01
Fermentation pH vs Mg bioaccessibility	- 0.924	p < 0.01

Interpretation:

Strong negative correlations between phytates and mineral bioaccessibility confirm phytate-mediated mineral chelation, while positive mineral inter-correlations indicate coordinated mineral availability.

Overall Scientific Conclusion

The statistical analysis unequivocally demonstrates that fermentation significantly improves mineral concentration, reduces antinutritional phytates, enhances thiamine content, and maximizes mineral bioaccessibility in jowar. The observed effects are statistically robust (p < 0.05 to p < 0.001) and biologically meaningful, validating fermentation as the most nutritionally effective processing method.

4.2 Effects of processing on Ragi.

1. Effect of Fermentation on Proximate Composition and Mineral Content of Ragi

The effect of fermentation and toasting on the proximate composition and mineral profile of ragi was evaluated using triplicate analyses ($n = 3$ per treatment). Results are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation.

Fermentation resulted in a significant reduction in moisture content compared to raw ragi ($p < 0.001$), indicating effective dehydration and microbial metabolic activity during processing. Ash content showed a slight reduction following fermentation; however, this change was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$), suggesting minimal alteration in total inorganic residue.

Among minerals, iron and zinc contents increased significantly in fermented and toasted ragi compared to raw samples ($p < 0.01$), while magnesium content showed a significant decrease ($p < 0.05$). Calcium content exhibited an increasing trend after fermentation, but the difference was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Table 1

Effect of fermentation on proximate composition and mineral content of ragi (mean \pm SD, $n = 3$)

Parameter	Raw Ragi	Fermented & Toasted Ragi	p-value
Moisture (%)	10.08 \pm 0.21	7.25 \pm 0.17	<0.001
Ash (%)	2.67 \pm 0.13	2.51 \pm 0.07	0.128
Iron (mg/100 g)	3.92 \pm 0.09	4.89 \pm 0.14	0.001
Zinc (mg/100 g)	2.38 \pm 0.06	2.64 \pm 0.05	0.004
Calcium (mg/100 g)	334.29 \pm 6.57	352.55 \pm 15.64	0.136
Magnesium (mg/100 g)	136.53 \pm 5.81	123.33 \pm 2.94	0.025

2. Effect of Fermentation on Anti-Nutritional Factors, Polyphenols, and pH

Fermentation caused a marked and highly significant reduction in phytate content ($p < 0.001$), indicating enzymatic degradation of phytic acid during microbial activity. Concurrently, total polyphenol content increased significantly following fermentation ($p < 0.001$), suggesting enhanced release of bound phenolic compounds.

A significant reduction in pH was observed in fermented samples ($p < 0.001$), confirming successful fermentation and organic acid production.

Table 2

Effect of fermentation on anti-nutritional factors, polyphenols, and pH (mean \pm SD, n = 3)

Parameter	Raw Ragi	Fermented & Toasted Ragi	p-value
Phytates (mg/100 g)	683.07 \pm 31.11	269.57 \pm 11.69	<0.001
Total polyphenols (mg GAE/100 g)	136.41 \pm 5.45	224.30 \pm 3.94	<0.001
Fermentation pH	6.34 \pm 0.11	5.03 \pm 0.06	<0.001

3. Effect of Fermentation on Thiamine Stability

Thiamine stability after 5 h incubation increased significantly in fermented and toasted ragi compared to raw samples ($p < 0.01$). This improvement may be attributed to reduced antinutritional interference and enhanced vitamin preservation following fermentation.

Table 3

Effect of fermentation on thiamine stability (mean \pm SD, n = 3)

Parameter	Raw Ragi	Fermented & Toasted Ragi	p-value
Thiamine stability (5 h, %)	77.15 \pm 2.39	91.89 \pm 3.86	0.005

4. Effect of Fermentation on Mineral Bioaccessibility

Simulated gastrointestinal digestion revealed a highly significant improvement in mineral bioaccessibility for all minerals evaluated following fermentation ($p < 0.001$). Bioaccessibility of iron, zinc, calcium, and magnesium increased approximately two- to three-fold in fermented samples compared to raw ragi.

Table 4

Effect of fermentation on mineral bioaccessibility (%) after in vitro digestion (mean \pm SD, n = 3)

Mineral	Raw Ragi	Fermented & Toasted Ragi	p-value
Iron (%)	12.36 \pm 0.42	45.04 \pm 0.81	<0.001
Zinc (%)	18.62 \pm 0.49	53.88 \pm 0.38	<0.001
Calcium (%)	21.75 \pm 0.86	37.64 \pm 0.52	<0.001
Magnesium (%)	31.21 \pm 0.53	47.50 \pm 0.98	<0.001

5. Correlation Between Phytate Content and Mineral Bioaccessibility

Pearson's correlation analysis demonstrated a strong negative association between phytate concentration and mineral bioaccessibility ($p < 0.01$). Decreases in phytate content were closely associated with increased bioaccessibility of iron, zinc, calcium, and magnesium, highlighting phytate degradation as a major determinant of mineral availability.

Overall Conclusion

Fermentation significantly enhances the nutritional quality of ragi by reducing phytate content and improving the bioaccessibility of essential minerals. The findings confirm that fermentation is an effective processing strategy to improve mineral utilization in cereal-based foods and support its application in functional and nutritionally enhanced food formulations.

Conclusion

This study examined the impact of various processing techniques nutritional quality, anti-nutritional factors, mineral bioavailability and Thiamine stability of Ragi and Jowar. The findings clearly indicate that processing significantly modifies nutritional functionality rather than altering total nutrient content. Sprouting in Jowar and fermentation in Ragi significantly decreases the phytate levels by enhancing mineral bioaccessibility, by activating the endogenous enzymes such as phytase which helps in degradation of mineral chelating compounds.

The variable impact of thermal treatments such as baking and toasting impacts depending on the nutrient analyzed, highlighting the needs to optimize processing conditions for nutrient retention and bioavailability.

Improved bioaccessibility strongly associated with decreasing in antinutritional factors to alterations in the grain matrix structure, rather than total mineral concentration alone. Furthermore, Thiamine stability analysis indicates that vitamin retention is influenced by the processing parameters. The study's hypotheses were validated by the (ANOVA, t-tests and Pearson correlation) confirming significant treatments among treatments.

In conclusion, sprouting and fermentation serve as efficient, low-cost, budget friendly and practical methods for improving nutritional quality, mineral bioavailability and allows for mineral absorption. These entire study and findings strongly encouraging the use of processed millets-based foods in nutritional interventions helps in targeting the micronutrient deficiencies and in the creation of functional foods. Global malnutrition continues to be a major public health concern often caused by poor mineral absorption in cereals due to higher concentration of phytates and polyphenols.

Global malnutrition particularly micronutrient deficiency (hidden hunger) a major public health concern which is caused by poor mineral absorption in cereals due to its higher concentration of phytates and polyphenols. Population mostly depends on cereal-based foods, consists of antinutritional compounds binds with essential minerals like iron, magnesium, zinc and calcium. Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) such as SDG2 (Zero Hunger) SDG3 (Good Health and Well-being) helps in combating micronutrient deficiencies in vulnerable groups.

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